

ISic0788

Epitaph for Cartilia Irene

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Found in excavations by Griffo in the 1940s in the area of the Necropolis of the Orti della Maddalena

Coordinates

38.183786, 15.549119

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3579

Physical Description

A slab of marble, missing the upper left corner and upper left margin, but otherwise intact (and the full text is preserved).

Dimensions

Height 29 cm

Width 26,5 cm

Depth cm

Layout

The text is approximately centered on the stone, with the left and right margins more or less regular except in the final two lines.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 25-30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1 to 6: 7-10 mm

Text

1. D(is) □ M(anibus) □
2. Cartilia □ Ire
3. ne □ vix(it) □ ann(is) □
4. XXXVIII □ Cl(audius) □ The
5. seus □ uxori □
6. sanctissimae

Apparatus

Text of Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

To the Shades of the Underworld. Cartilia Irene lived 38 years. Claudius Theseus to (his) most pure wife

Translation (it)

Alle ombre dell'aldilà. Cartilia Irene visse 38 anni. Claudio Teseo per la (sua) purissima moglie

Commentary

Three other texts from the same necropolis were also set up by Claudius Thesis, two in Greek (ISic3529 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3529>] , ISic3530 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3530>]) and a second in Latin (ISic0787 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0787>]).

Digital identifiers:

TM 175709

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PHI 313653

Bibliography

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